

ATTITUDES OF TEACHERS, STUDENTS AND PARENTS TOWARDS FLEXIBLE ONLINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at describing the attitudes of teachers, students, parents of accredited private university in one of the City in the Philippines. A total of 331 respondents participated in this study. The descriptive cross-sectional method of research was used to gather data. Three sets of survey questionnaires were utilized. Data gathered were analysed and interpreted using weighted mean, correlation and one-way ANOVA. Findings of the study revealed that respondents are prepared in most aspects of needed capabilities and technology for online learning. More so, with regards to attitudes of respondents, they believe that online class is a good option during any crisis situation and time is manageable using this modality yet there are improvements needed to provide better provisions for online modality. It was also found out that there is no significant relationship between readiness and attitudes. Likewise, comparing attitudes of three groups towards online schooling showed that there is no significant difference among attitudes of the respondents.

Keywords: *Attitude, online schooling, flexible learning, synchronous learning, asynchronous learning, descriptive research*

INTRODUCTION

Online schooling or distance learning modality has gained popularity and attention especially in the time of pandemic when people are not allowed for social gatherings and should only stay in the confines of their homes.

One study about technology used was done by Zhu ET. Al., (2018) suggested that educational benefits of technology usage were the key factor influencing both students' and parents' attitudes. Based on the cross-examined understanding of parents' and students' attitudes, suggestions for large scale tablet initiatives are proposed. But the study of attitudes in this particular case is done in a traditional face to face setting that differentiates with the current study.

When unprecedented problems on how the schooling will be undertaken without disruption of educational operations and practices for the learning to thrive, one of the most popular and convenient way to employ teaching and learning is online schooling using technologies and online platforms with digital pedagogies (Milton, 2013).

There are echoing clamor also on some quarters of the society asking for academic freeze due to lack of preparations, resources and digital divides among students and teachers. Prior to school opening, DepEd initiated more urgent online trainings and webinars about online modalities and technology usage yet unable to pursue a total implementation of online approach. But other schools especially private institutions adopted the online modality as the best option to deliver learning using Learning Management System with synchronous, asynchronous and hybrid format during pandemic.

Since distance education finds its significance more so in this time of pandemic, schools should be aware of perspectives, feelings, expectations and needs of students, parents and teachers. The attitudes of these significant characters play a role in the achievement and improvement of educational process. Conclusions that will be drawn in this study will be useful for the academic community and everyone concerned with the planning, development and implementation of strategies for online learning and distance education in a campus based university in a transition to distance education (Peytcheva-Forsyth, 2018).

One study about attitude dwelt on Science subject being influenced by pedagogical skills of teachers (Benson, Nwagbo, Ugwuanyi, & Okeke, (2020). Attitudes of parents, teachers and students are determined in this study in the absence or fragment of empirical data about this subject. The result of the study is expected to be significant to introduce improvement of the online program with the data that will be obtained as basis.

Research Objectives

1. Describe the readiness of the respondents in using flexible/online learning mode.
2. Describe the prevailing attitudes of parents, teachers and students towards flexible learning modality.
3. Determine the relationship between the readiness and attitude of parents, teachers and students in flexible/online learning mode.
4. Compare the attitudes of parents, teachers and students towards flexible/online learning
5. What are the improvements that are needed in flexible/ online schooling as perceived by the respondents?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between readiness and attitudes of parents, teachers and students on flexible/online learning mode.
2. There is no significant difference among attitudes of parents, teachers and students towards flexible/online learning mode.

METHODOLOGY

This study which is quantitative in nature utilized the descriptive inferential research design. This design is a systematic approach to inquiry that involves description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of conditions that now exist. According to Baraceros (2016), descriptive research aims at defining or giving a verbal portrayal or picture of a person, thing, event, group, situation, etc. This design was used in this study in describing the attitude of junior high school parents, teachers and students of an accredited private junior high school. Descriptive statistics describes data and inferential statistics allows you to make predictions (“inferences”) from that data. With inferential statistics, you take data from samples and make generalizations about a population (Statisticshowto, 2023). As regards the utilization of the descriptive correlation as inferential statistics design, Sousa, Driessnack, & Mendes (2007) explain that descriptive correlational studies describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. They involve the systematic investigation of the nature of relationships, or associations between and among variables, rather than direct cause-effect relationships. Correlations analyze direction, degree, magnitude, and strength of the relationships or associations.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in one accredited Private Accredited University in the Philippines where online schooling is adopted as the mode of teaching and learning. Teachers, parents and students underwent training and orientation about online modality. The school with established Learning Management System and provides distance learning has been preferred by parents and students in times of pandemic when face to face is not an option. Online mode using LMS also allows certain flexibilities and thus also termed as Flexible Learning. There is uncertainty and absence of idea how online learning works if fully implemented during pandemic and thus parents, students and teachers alike have their attitude which may be derived from their perspectives, ideas, beliefs or feelings towards a phenomenon. This is the reason why the attitude of the respondents towards online class needs to be examined as a way of determining the possible success or failure of an online program and find solutions for the formulation of policy and programs for improvement.

Participants of the Study

The respondents of the study were the teachers, students and parents of one of the Private Accredited University in the Philippines. A total of 10 teachers, 139 students

and 182 parents participated in this study. The samples were taken from the population using stratified random sampling method.

There are three strata where the samples are taken from each group different from each other. Everyone in the group has given a chance to be participants in the study.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Teachers	40
Students	139
Parents	182
Total	361

The Research Instruments

Structured survey questionnaires were used to collect data using Google form for this study. There were three (3) sets of questionnaires used in the study for teachers, students and parents. The questionnaires include readiness survey, attitude survey for teachers, students, and parents, suggestions and recommendations survey for teachers, students and parents.

The weighted means of responses to the questionnaire were verbally described using the following scale:

- 1 (if there is negative perception due to the falsity of what the item describes)
- 2 (if there is non-conformity to the item describes)
- 3 – (if there is somehow conformity to what the item describes)
- 4– (if there is strong conformity to the truthfulness and manifestation of what the item describes)

The weighted mean of responses to the scales were verbally described as follows.

Numerical equivalent	Verbal Description
3.25-4.00	Strongly agree
2.50-3.24	Agree
1.75-2.49	Disagree
1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the permission from the administration of the accredited University in one of the Cities through request letters. The questionnaires were sent to the respondents via group chat in messenger. The link for Google form has been sent to the respondents. The questionnaires were retrieved and tallied later. Thereafter the results were recorded, organized, then analyzed and interpreted.

Validity and Reliability

The validity of the instruments was determined with the help of a statistician. The proponent also consulted other experts in the field to establish the validity of the instruments. Using the data taken from a school in one of the City in the Philippines with the same characteristics to the subject respondents, the questionnaire for students, parents and teachers were administered beforehand to determine the instrument's reliability. With the assistance of a statistician through careful examination, conclusion arrived at that items of the instruments were clear and the directions are well –stated. The data gathered revealed a strong reliability coefficient.

Analysis of Data

Using descriptive statistical tools the data gathered were then analyzed. The weighted mean of the responses with regard to readiness survey, attitude survey, problems and benefits survey questionnaires as well as the correlation between readiness and attitude and difference among attitudes of respondents were tabulated and computed then later on analyzed and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2
Readiness of the Respondents in Online Schooling

Item/s	Teachers		Parents		Students	
	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description
1. I can use email, internet , messenger with ease	3.90	SA	3.2	A	3.3	SA
2. I have enough knowledge on how to use google apps and internet browsers	3.70	SA	3.2	A	3.1	A

3. I felt confident in using LMS required by School	3.40	SA	3.1	A	3.1	A
4. I am technology savvy.	3.10	A	2.8	A	3.0	A
5. The school trained me well in online teaching mode.	3.10	A	3.0	A	3.1	A
6. I am very familiar and skilled in using features of Learning Management System	3.00	A	2.9	A	3.2	A
7. I have gadget/s which is/are adequate for online teaching	3.60	SA	3.3	SA	3.3	SA
8. I can use communication tools proficiently such as Zoom, Google Meet, BigBlueButton etc.	3.80	SA	3.2	A	3.4	SA
9. I can effectively create tutorial videos	3.00	A	2.8	A	2.9	A
10. I can construct modules, syllabus, learning contents and assessment materials effectively in LMS.	3.50	SA	3.0	A	3.2	A
11. I have strong internet connection	3.20	A	2.6	A	2.5	A
12. I am very much ready to teach using online modality.	3.40	SA	2.8	A	2.9	A
Overall Weighted mean	3.39	SA	2.99	A	3.10	A

In this study, readiness of the respondents achieves certain degree of positive response although not to the apex limit. It means that although they agree that they have certain degree of preparation for online schooling something more must be done for improvement. Yet, for a school that is starting to adapt, noticing that stakeholders have capability to utilize technologies is not a bad start at all.

The current K12 online program is still awash of turbulent waters of regional politics, temperamental technologies, innovative methods with no test of efficacy (Ronsisvalle and Watkins, 2005). Readiness to a certain extent provides avenue that sets

the motivation of the learners, parents and students to a positive level. In the absence or lack of it, the ability to deliver and achieve the learning goals may suffer.

As teachers acknowledge both the positive and negative sides of technology as it influences how we learn and survive, it is crucial to strike a balance between social or emotional pedagogy and the pedagogy of inclusion and integration of technology (McFarlane, 2011). Thus, technology plays a vital role as significant component in the implementation of online modality. The level of preparation will somehow define the level of adaptation.

Table 3
Survey of Respondents Attitudes towards Online Class

Item/s	Teachers		Students		Parents	
	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description
1. It is fun teaching online class.	2.90	A	2.8	A	2.7	A
2. There is lesser work in online class.	2.00	D	2.8	A	3.0	A
3. Teaching experiences are more effective in online class.	2.00	D	2.3	D	2.4	D
4. It is easy to manage time with less synchronous schedules in online class.	3.10	A	2.9	A	2.9	A
5. There are adequate interactions in Online Class.	2.30	A	2.9	A	2.8	A
6 Cheating is easy to manage in online modality.	2.80	A	3.0	A	2.8	A
7. I find it cheaper and minimize my expenses working at home	2.70	A	2.9	A	2.9	A
8. I can easily cope with the digital skills required in teaching.	3.10	A	3.1	A	2.8	A
9. Preparing modules, syllabus and exams became simpler and systematic.	2.70	A	2.9	A	2.9	A
10. Online class is the better option during pandemic.	3.50	SA	3.3	SA	3.3	SA
11. There are fewer interruptions in teaching online.	2.40	D	2.6	A	2.8	A

12. I can manage my time well in this modality	3.50	SA	2.9	A	2.8	A
13. Teaching online is satisfying.	2.40	D	2.7	A	2.6	A
14. I can employ diverse teaching method well	2.70	A	2.9	A	2.9	A
15. Problems online can easily be solved.	2.20	D	2.9	A	2.5	A
Overall Weighted Mean	2.69	A	2.86	A	2.79	A

It is interesting to note that flexible/online class schooling is said to be the better option during pandemic. This highlighted in the study of Dhawan (2020) which expressed that this pandemic situation challenged the education system across the world and forced educators to shift to an online mode of teaching overnight. Many academic institutions that were earlier reluctant to change their traditional pedagogical approach had no option but to shift entirely to online teaching–learning.

Likewise, it is also revealing that effectiveness of teaching experiences in online class obtained flak. This may be due to the factors involving limitation in internet and interactions. Online class is also considered arduous among students, teachers, and parents. That is why Gilbert (2015) stressed in his study the challenges of online schooling which are hurdles among stakeholders but definitive measures can be undertaken to overcome those and increase the efficacy of teaching-and-learning methods that have been adversely affected and ensure that students do not fall behind (Aliyyah et al., 2020).

Table 4
Relationship between the Readiness and Attitude of Teachers, Parents, and Students

Correlations		Attitude of Teachers
Readiness of Teachers	Pearson Correlation	-0.208
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.564
	N	10
Relationship between the Readiness and Attitude of Parents		Attitude of Parents
Correlations		
Readiness of Parents	Pearson Correlation	.398**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0
	N	182
Relationship between the Readiness and Attitude of Students		
Correlations		

Readiness of Students	Pearson Correlation	Attitude of Students
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.429**
	N	0
		139

Table shows the relationship of readiness and attitudes of teachers, parents and students. Since our computed Pearson r for parents is .398 and students Pearson r is .429 at significant level of .05, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is significant relationship between readiness and attitudes towards online/flexible learning based on the response of parents and students. However, based on the lens of teachers the result is the opposite.

Varied findings on different variables revealed in the study of Tang (2013) that first, the use of technology in education was not a hindrance to the students. Second, blended learning adaptability, which was modelled as a second-order formative construct and formed by four first-order reflective constructs—attitude towards online learning, study management, online interaction, and learning flexibility—had a positive relationship with student readiness for blended learning. Third, attitude towards classroom learning had a negative relationship with student readiness for blended learning. An understanding of student attitude towards different learning aspects can be critical in the assessment of student readiness for blended learning, which is a prerequisite for successful implementation of blended learning.

The findings show that having readiness follows that positive attitude also echo among students and parents. Increase readiness links to developing encouraging attitudes. Respondents' readiness amounted to their feelings, beliefs or perspectives towards an issue or phenomenon. The result established that whenever there is a greater extent of preparation, an affirmative or positive attitude manifests which tantamount to better cooperation, motivation and collaboration among key players in education. On the other hand, this is in contrary to the response of the teachers. Further study in other context is suggested to explore additional findings which will prove or disprove the current findings.

Table 5
ONEWAY Attitude on Online Schooling by Groups

/MISSING ANALYSIS
 /POSTHOC=TUKEY
 ALPHA(0.05).

ANOVA					
Attitude On Flexible Learning					
	Sum of Squares	df	Weighted mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.581	2	0.291	1.655	0.193
Within Groups	57.604	328	0.176		
Total	58.185	330			

Table shows the result of comparison among attitudes of teachers, students and parents using one -way ANOVA. It shows that p value 0.193 is greater than .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among attitudes of teachers, students and parents. Researches however affirmed that there is a difference among attitudes of stakeholders with regards to using new technologies in school which includes online modality.

In particular, the study of Al-Emran, Elsherif and Shaalan (2016) different factors have been examined to test where there is a significant difference among students and educators' attitudes towards the use of M-learning, such as gender, age, country, level of study, smartphone ownership, major in terms of students and age, country, academic rank, academic experience and smartphone ownership in terms of educators. Findings revealed significant differences among the students' attitudes towards M-learning with regard to their smartphone ownership, country and age. Furthermore, results indicated that M-learning can be one of the promising pedagogical technologies to be employed.

It contradicts with the findings of this study that attitudes of the respondents do not vary. It implies that they have common beliefs and feelings towards online schooling. The unanimity of the respondents' attitude implies that their perception, beliefs and feelings towards online schooling maybe due to their common experiences in the implementation of online modality.

Table 8
Improvements needed for Online Schooling as Perceived by the Respondents

Item	Teachers		Parents		Students	
	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description	Weighted mean	Description
1. Activities in online class should be organized better	3.6	SA	3.4	SA	3.3	SA
2. Provide more training about digital platform.	3.8	SA	3.2	A	3.3	SA
3. Provide Psycho-social support	3.6	SA	3.4	SA	3.3	SA
4. Remedial classes and exams be provided	3.8	SA	3.4	SA	3.3	SA
5. More parents consultations and interactions	3.8	SA	3.2	A	3.1	A
6. Provision for strong internet connections for teachers.	3.8	SA	3.4	SA	3.4	SA
7. Reduce teachers paper works to focus more on mastery of delivery	3.6	SA	3.5	SA	3.3	SA
8. Reduce screen-time exposure to both teachers and students	3.8	SA	3.5	SA	3.3	SA
9. Provide parents training on effective engagement in online modality.	3.6	SA	3.2	A	3.2	A
10. Incorporate learning technologies in strategic plan	3.8	SA	3.4	SA	3.3	SA
Overall Weighted mean	3.72	SA	3.34	SA	3.27	SA

Based on the result it is affirmed that online schooling can be improved as a matter of change in policies, provisions, and programs. Aside from the things commonly regarded as beneficial for the improvements of online learning such as establishing norms, creating accessible content, strengthening relationship, fostering lively interactions and connecting with families (Nielsen, 2020) there are other concerns that

are recognized to be of utmost needs to be included in the program of instituting technologies like using online modality in teaching and learning.

Findings above show the strong sentiment of respondents that provisions of giving emphasis on those items mentioned above are necessary especially when it comes to provision of strong internet connections. This is manifested as they strongly agree on most items enumerated.

Conclusions

1. Teachers, students and parents are prepared on online modality. This concurs with the pre-survey result conducted by the school to the clients before resorting to online class modality.
2. There is significant relationship between readiness and attitude.
3. There is no significant difference among attitudes of teachers, parents and students.
4. There are benefits in online schooling yet improvements are needed including more provisions for upgrade and enrichment of facilities, resources and technologies as perceived by the respondents.

Recommendations

1. Strengthen the program for online schooling by providing the stakeholders with support and good provisions for learning online.
2. Incorporate upgrade of learning technologies and capabilities to strategic plan
3. Provide teachers with resources and flexibility
4. Accommodate suggestions from stakeholders to improve the online learning program, make it adequate and effective to build positive attitudes towards online schooling for its success.
5. Have the evaluation of the online program which includes monitoring of the effectiveness involving the stakeholders, teachers, parents and students whose attitudes are affected by how effective or adequate the program is.
6. This study may be administered in other settings and contexts to find out more data regarding online schooling using the same or other variables with varied participants and stakeholders.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researcher obtained the informed consent from all participants involved in the study, including students, faculty, and parents and clearly stated the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, the potential risks and benefits, and the participants' rights to voluntary participation, withdrawal, and confidentiality.

The identity and anonymity of the respondents are considered. They were aware of the purpose of the study and that the data gathered will only be used primarily for research. The privacy of participants records are considered and ensure that any personal information or sensitive data collected during the study is handled securely in accordance with Data Privacy Act. Necessary permission were secured and complied with before collecting data.

The proponent assured that research design, procedures, and interventions prioritize the well-being, convenience, comfort and best interests of participants by minimizing potential hazards, distress, conflict with work schedules or risks associated with participating in the study. This study promotes equity and inclusion by taking into account the diverse backgrounds, needs, perspectives, culture and status of participants. Researcher avoids any form of discrimination, stigma or bias in the research process and efforts are made with due diligence to include underrepresented groups and ensure equitable access to research opportunities.

Cooperation and respect are established by respectful and cooperative relationship with participants and the school. Researcher also acknowledged and values the contributions of participants and ensures that their voices and experiences are accurately expressed and interpreted in the research results. Research is conducted with integrity, honesty and transparency and devoid any fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism by adhering to ethical guidelines to maintain the integrity and trustworthiness of data based on the result.

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REFERENCES:

- Baraceros, E.L. (2016). Practical Research 1. Rex Book Store. 2016. Quezon City.
- Benson, O. O., Nwagbo, C. R., Ugwuanyi, C. S., & Okeke, C. I. O. (2020). Students' perception of teachers' pedagogical skills and its influence on their attitude towards science: implication for science, technology and engineering careers. *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development (IJMPERD)*, 10(3), 14701-14714.
- Al-Emran, M., Elsherif, H. M., & Shaalan, K. (2016). Investigating attitudes towards the use of mobile learning in higher education. *Computers in Human behavior*, 56, 93-102
- Aliyyah, R. R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. R. S. (2020). The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90-109.
- Gilbert, B. (2015). Online learning revealing the benefits and challenges. <https://www.statisticshowto.com/> date retrieved 04/02/2023
- McFarlane, D. A. (2011). A comparison of organizational structure and pedagogical approach: Online versus face-to-face. *Journal of Educators Online*, 8(1), n1.
- Milton, M., (2013) *Journal of Literacy and Technology* 72 Volume 14, Number 1: March 2013 ISSN: 1535-0975 Digital literacy and digital pedagogies for teaching literacy: Pre-service teachers' experience on teaching rounds. Digital literacy and digital pedagogies for teaching literacy: Pre-service teachers' experience on teaching rounds.

- Nielsen, L. (2020) Effective Online Learning Practices Developing best practices for online learning <https://www.techlearning.com/tl-advisor-blog/8>
- Peytcheva-Forsyth, R., Yovkova, B., & Aleksieva, L. (2018). Factors affecting students' attitudes towards online learning - The case of Sofia University. doi:10.1063/1.5082043
- Ronsisvalle, T., & Watkins, R. (2005). Student success in online K-12 education. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 6(2), 117.
- Sousa, V. D., Driesnack, M. Mendez, I.A.C. (2007). An overview of research designs relevant to nursing: Part 1: Quantitative research designs. *Revista latino-Americana de enfermagem*.ISSN 1518-8345.<https://doi.org/10.1590/SO104-11692007000300022>. On-line version ISSN 1518-8345
- Zhu S., Yang H., MacLeod J., Shi Y., and Wu D. (2018) Parents' and Students' Attitudes toward Tablet Integration in Schools *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning* Volume 19, Number 4 ,September – 2018
- Tang, C. (2013). READINESS FOR BLENDED LEARNING: UNDERSTANDING ATTITUDE OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS. *International journal of cyber society and education*. 6. 79-100. 10.7903/ijcse.1086.